

At a Glance

Acronym: RAISE

Title: Research Analysis Identifier System

Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01

Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-04

Project number: 101058479

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Project duration: 40 months

Start Date: 1 October 2022

Project Coordinator: Lab of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

The real value of **open data** for the **research community** is not to access them but to **process** them as conveniently as possible in order to **reduce time-to-result** and **increase productivity**. To that end, the **RAISE project will** provide the infrastructure for a **distributed crowdsourced data processing system**, moving from open data to **open access data** for **processing**. It will render the **mechanism** for sending the algorithm to the dataset instead of sending the data to the algorithm.

Contact us

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Consortium

The **RAISE consortium** consists of **20 partners** from **10 countries** which namely are **Greece, Spain, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Italy, Cyprus, Sweden, Belgium, United Kingdom, Canada**

RAISE partners provide the project with **technical** (*AUTH, VICOM, INTRA, CERTH, UoWM, UoM, TCR, WITA, CLPT*), **scientific** (*AUTH, VICOM, CERTH, AINIGMA, UoWM, UoM, SOTON, McGill*), **innovation and exploitation** (*VILABS, ATHENA, OpenAIRE*) experience.

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Enabling Data Analysis without Data Sharing

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The challenge

The **European Research Data Landscape** study looks at researchers' practices in **producing, reusing and depositing data**, and in making it **FAIR** (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable access to research data*), as well as examining the **research data repository landscape**. The findings of the study show that while certain **FAIR practices** are being adopted and researchers are motivated by the ideals of **Open Science, obstacles still remain to making data FAIR**.

What does RAISE address?

RAISE aspires to build a **trustful and transparent environment** where **research communities** can **share and process data** as conveniently as possible in order to **reduce time-to-result** and **increase productivity**. With **RAISE**, the researchers can **publish their outcomes** with **evidence-based authenticity** of the data-analysis performed ensuring at the same time **accreditation** of their work.

RAISE Pilots

Within the broad domain of **Open Data Science**, RAISE will test and assess the effectiveness of RAISE system in real life use cases in the following **scientific domains**:

Health

Environment

Mobility

Cross-disciplinary

Who benefits from RAISE?

Researchers (data providers):

- Accreditation of their contribution
- Data plagiarism for originality and ownership

Researchers (data processors):

- More data to be processed available
- Available processing resources from the community
- Tools for replicability and reproducibility

EOSC community:

- Onboarding of RAISE services in the EOSC service catalogue and portal
- Uptake by the community and long-term sustainability of RAISE services in the EOSC ecosystem

Publishers:

- More transparent peer review process
- RAI identifier as a new tool of trust for scientific publications

Open Data Repositories:

- Can easily adopt RAISE and offer more services

RAISE Innovative Services & Outputs

RAISE introduces the **Research Analysis Identifier** (RAI) and services that will support trustworthy research and data analysis services based on crowd-sourced distributed resources along with local resources. Particularly, RAISE will produce the following **Outputs**:

1. RAI Certified nodes: A trustworthy crowdsourced network offering data storing and processing resources (community resources). The network will also provide the mechanisms for ensuring originality and authentication of data assets and research results.

2. RAI Cloud: Orchestrates the data sharing, processing, and finding.

3. The Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) a unique identifier of any result along with the dataset information and the processing script (RAI Registration Service), without disclosing any source code or raw data.

4. Dataset plagiarism identification and dataset proof-of-origin services, to maximize the level of trust of the RAISE system.

5. RAI Synthetic Data Generator and the RAI SDK to help researchers develop processing scripts by getting access to sample, small scale datasets which mock real data.